

LATERAL INTERNAL SPHINCTEROTOMY VS BOTOX INJECTION FOR TREATMENT OF CHRONIC ANAL FISSURE

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Abstract

Objective:

To compare the effectiveness in terms of cure rates for chronic anal fissure treatment.

Methods:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the General Surgery Unit of Mayo Hospital, Lahore. We included 60 patients with a diagnosis of chronic anal fissure aged 18 to 70 years from December 2024 to April 2025. In the first group (Group A), the open method was employed for lateral internal sphincterotomy (LIS). In the second group (Group B), patients received an injection of botulinum toxin A. frequency of complete healing was determined at 21st day of treatment.

Results:

The LIS group had a mean age of 37.57 years (\pm 12.82), while the Botox group had a mean age of 40.8 years (\pm 11.32), resulting in a *p*-value of 0.30. In terms of gender distribution, the LIS group had 21 males (70%) and 9 females (30%), while the Botox group consisted of 18 males (60%) and 12 females (40%), with a *p*-value of 0.58. The LIS group demonstrated a successful healing rate of 28 (93.3%), significantly higher than the Botox group, which had a success rate of 19 (63.3%), *p*-value 0.004.

Conclusion:

The rate of complete healing of anal fistula is significantly higher in patients treated with LIS in comparison to patients receiving Botox injection.

INTRODUCTION

An anal fissure refers to a small tear in the lining of the anal canal located just below the dentate line. This condition is quite common and, while not serious, can lead to considerable discomfort and pain.¹ Anal fissures can be classified as either acute

or chronic. An acute fissure is typically a fresh tear, while a chronic fissure appears as a more established ulcer, characterized by rough, scarred edges and visible muscle fibers from the internal anal sphincter at its base.² The precise cause of anal fissures remains

unclear; however, they are often associated with factors such as constipation leading to hard stools or trauma to the anal area, which can elevate the resting pressure within the anal region.³

Managing anal fissures involves various approaches, including lifestyle and dietary changes, as well as medical and surgical interventions. The initial step typically includes adopting a high-fiber diet and using medications such as topical nitroglycerin or calcium channel blockers.⁴ These are regarded as the first-line treatments. When conservative methods fail, surgery may be considered, with lateral internal sphincterotomy (LIS) being the preferred procedure for many patients. Other surgical options, like advancement flaps, are selectively used in certain cases.^{5, 6} Recently, botulinum toxin injections have gained popularity as a non-surgical alternative, showing promising results in treating anal fissures effectively.^{7, 8}

Both of these treatment options have their own pros and cons. Lateral Internal Sphincterotomy (LIS) has shown high rates of fissure healing, which is a significant advantage. However, it carries the downside of potential complications, such as the risk of anal incontinence, which is a significant concern for patients. On the other hand, Botulinum A toxin injection, a non-surgical approach, has demonstrated eff, effectiveness in promoting healing without the risk of incontinence. But, the downside is that its benefits might be temporary, necessitating repetitive injections for sustained relief.⁹ To address this knowledge gap and provide valuable insights specific to our setting, our study aims to compare the effectiveness in terms of cure rates for chronic anal fissure treatment through well-designed RCTs

METHODS:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the General Surgery Unit of Mayo Hospital, Lahore. We included 60 patients with a diagnosis of chronic anal fissure aged 18 to 70 years from December 2024 to April 2025. Patients with colorectal malignancy, tuberculosis, inflammatory bowel disease, or those having anomalies of the colorectal region were excluded.

Patients were allocated to two groups through a randomization process using Microsoft Excel's random number generation feature, ensuring each

group had an equal number of participants. In the first group (Group A), the open method was employed for lateral internal sphincterotomy (LIS). After administering suitable anesthesia and positioning the patient appropriately under sterile conditions, the surgical procedure was carried out. An incision was made at either the 3 o'clock or 9 o'clock position, and the fibers of the internal anal sphincter were carefully elevated and divided. In the second group (Group B), patients received an injection of botulinum toxin A. The toxin was administered on both sides of the anal fissure, with a total dose of 40 IU (0.4 ml), directly into the sphincter muscle after providing adequate analgesia and anesthesia if necessary.

These patients were followed in Outdoor department weekly for 21 days by the operating team and primary outcome variable; successful healing was determined.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS v25. Chi-square test was applied to compare the successful healing rate between the groups at p-value ≤ 0.05 as a significant difference.

RESULTS:

The LIS group had a mean age of 37.57 years (± 12.82), while the Botox group had a mean age of 40.8 years (± 11.32), resulting in a p-value of 0.30. The duration of fissures among the LIS group was approximately 6.90 months (± 6.48), compared to 8.73 months (± 7.35) in the Botox group, with a p-value of 0.31. In terms of gender distribution, the LIS group had 21 males (70%) and 9 females (30%), while the Botox group consisted of 18 males (60%) and 12 females (40%), with a p-value of 0.58. Additionally, the prevalence of diabetes was noted in 6 individuals (20.0%) from the LIS group and 7 individuals (23.3%) from the Botox group, resulting in a p-value of 0.75. Lastly, hypertension was present in 4 participants (13.3%) in the LIS group and in 6 participants (20.0%) in the Botox group, with a p-value of 0.48 (Table 1).

In the study, the LIS group demonstrated a successful healing rate of 93.3% (28 out of 30 participants), significantly higher than the Botox group, which had a success rate of 63.3% (19 out of 30), with a p-value of 0.004 (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline Study Characteristics.

	LIS Group (N=30)	Botox Group (N=30)	P-value
Age (Years)	37.57±12.82	40.8±11.32	0.30
Duration of Fissure (months)	6.90±6.48	8.73±7.35	0.31
Gender (male/Female) (%)	21 (70%) / 9 (30%)	18 (60%) / 12 (40%)	0.58
Diabetes (%)	6 (20.0%)	7 (23.3%)	0.75
Hypertension (%)	4 (13.3%)	6 (20.0%)	0.48

Table 2. Comparison of Study Outcomes.

Successful Healing	LIS Group (N=30)	Botox Group (N=30)	P-value
Yes (%)	28 (93.3%)	19 (63.3%)	0.004
No (%)	02 (6.7%)	11 (36.7%)	

DISCUSSION:

An anal fissure is defined as a linear tear in the anoderm located below the dentate line.¹⁰ These fissures can occur due to the passage of hard stools or as a consequence of prolonged episodes of diarrhea.¹¹ When a tear occurs in the anoderm, the internal anal sphincter responds by tightening, which can create further discomfort, exacerbate the tear, and decrease blood circulation to the affected area. This cycle can prevent proper healing, leading to the development of a chronic fissure.¹²

Anal fissures often cause significant discomfort for patients, largely due to their painful symptoms and the social stigma attached to the condition, which can prevent individuals from openly discussing their struggles.¹³ Given that this condition is challenging to treat and often recurs, it is crucial to investigate all possible treatment methods and interventions that could effectively alleviate the issue. This study aimed to compare the results of two treatment options that have shown promise in addressing this condition.

Majority of our patients were of young age with mean age of 37 to 40 years. Recent research parallels this trend, with studies by Rahbar et al. and Rahman et al. highlighting that patients suffering from anal fissures predominantly fall within a specific age group. The highest incidence is observed among individuals aged 31 to 40 years. This suggests a potential age-related vulnerability or risk factor associated with this condition.^{14, 15}

This research revealed a significant gender disparity, with males comprising approximately 65% of the studied population. This trend aligns with findings by Sakr et al., who observed that males represented about 58% of individuals affected by the condition.¹⁶ In contrast, Bara et al. reported that females were more frequently affected, accounting for roughly 53.8% of cases involving anal fissures.¹⁷

In this study the healing rate of fistula was high in LIS group; 93.3% in comparison to 63.3% in botox group. Similar results were reported by Shoaib et al., who reported a fistula healing rate of 95.24% using LIS and 73.81% using Botox injection. Moreover a recent meta-analysis by Bonyad et al. including 18 studies and 1839 patients reported that LIS had a significantly higher healing rates in comparison to Botox injection.¹⁸

The present study shows that healing rates are higher with LIS, but both procedures are equally safe. Therefore, because of ease of performance and reduced invasiveness, it is recommended that patients with chronic anal fissure initially receive botulinum toxin therapy, and LIS should only be performed if this treatment fails. The study had no limitations other than a shorter follow-up period, which prevented assessment of the recurrence rate.

CONCLUSION:

The rate of complete healing of anal fistula is significantly higher in patients treated with LIS in comparison to patients receiving Botox injection.

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